

ISic3132

I.Sicily inscription 3132

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Monte Adranone

Provenance

room 2b of large building at foot of acropolis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Monte Adranone

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330191

1. . . MIAΣ.Δ.[O]PON.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645473

PHI 330191

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 28.0768

De Miro, E., Fiorentini, G. 1976-1977. Relazione sull'attività della Soprintendenza

alle antichità di Agrigento (1972-1976). *Kokalos*. 22-23: 423-455. At 453 tav.48
fig.3

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